

The decorated shelters along the Amilianga trail (Ennedi, Chad)

Ancillary Data to *The Archaic and Niola Doa-like paintings of the Eli-1 shelter (Ennedi, Chad)*

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Abstract: Paintings attributable to the recent Bovine and recent Camel periods decorate five small shelters carved into the rocky sides of the Amilianga trail, south of the Eli-1 rock art site. The most interesting motifs in the inventory comprehend women with bell-shaped hairstyles in Eli-2, women dancing hands in hands in Amilianga-2 and a human figure with an animal-shaped head in Amilianga-3. Well-polished engravings of camels with the humps schematised as triangles are also present in the open, at the entrance of the Amilianga-2 shelter.

Keywords: rock art, painting, cattle, camel, Eli, Amilianga, Ennedi, Chad

Figure 1. Location map of the decorated shelters in the area of the Amilianga pass. E01, E02 and E03 stand for Eli-1, Eli-2 and Eli-3. A01, A02, and A03 stand for Amilianga-1, Amilianga-2 and Amilianga-3. The satellite image in the background is from Digital Globe - Google Earth©.

The rock art sites near the Eli-1 shelter, at the Amilianga pass

The Eli-2 shelter

At the base of the rocky spur hosting Eli-1, toward the dune blocking the Amilianga pass, a small shelter opens to the west (Fig. 2). The entrance is less than 2 meters wide by 3 meters high. An oblique fracture subdivides into two panels the southern shelter wall (Fig. 3).

The most evident paintings decorating the left panel are two warriors mounted on horseback. These depictions of equestrians, clearly superimposing smaller cattle figures, are attributable to the recent Camel Period on a comparison basis with the Erichigué I site (Bailloud 1997).

Figure 2. The Eli-2 shelter is a small cavity, two by three meters large at the entrance. Paintings decorate the southern sidewall.

Figure 3. On the southern sidewall of the Eli-2 shelter, standing warriors with round hairstyles, women with bell-shaped hairstyles, and small-sized figures, perhaps young individuals, suggest the living portrait of a small community. To the left, depictions of warriors mounted on horseback, superimpose cattle figures. The muzzle, the ears and the mane of the upper horse have been accurately redrawn and repainted in white (the IFRAO colour scale bar is 10 cm).

The panel extending to the right, towards the cave entrance, comprehends at its mid-left height a tight group of nine standing men and women. White dots represent the eyes painted at the top of sticky heads (Fig. 4). Men wear loincloths and hold spears. Long feathers, recumbent at the top end, complete their round

headdresses. Masculine body decorations consist of white vertical lines painted on the trunk, branching around the neck, and white horizontal thin stripes painted at the knees level.

Bell-shaped hairstyles feature the women wearing long skirts. Women clothing accessories comprehend necklaces with multiple beaded lines and double belts painted in white. Patterns of white angled lines decorate the chest (or possibly the tunic) of the two women at the group centre.

The height of the nine figures varies, may be according to the social status or class age, with one warrior appearing by size as the prominent individual.

Below this outstanding group, the composition develops in a sequence of smaller figures composed by two kneeling women working on the grinding stone near triangular white huts with a topping closing device painted in red. A small woman carrying a pot and small men figures shown in a diminutive size, likely representing little boys and girls, are depicted in-between. More to the right, on the same register, a standing woman and two warriors close the sequence. Small round shields are shown near the warriors' feet.

Human figures are evidently the most represented motifs in Eli-2 but a cow and its calf, featured by a coat decorated with a geometric pattern, occupy the focal point of the panel. A group of two warriors and a standing woman sides this peculiar cattle scene to the extreme right (Fig. 3). Very interestingly, this kind of composition, praising a particular cow with its calf by assigning them the central spot and placing people around, has a good correspondence in the Panel C of the Chéiré-1 painted shelter (Menardi Noguera and Bonomo 2014).

Figure 4. Tiny white dots depict the eyes of men and women in the mid-left group scene painted on the western wall of the Eli-2 shelter.

A group of paintings, quite heterogeneous in style, crowds the upper border of the panel (Fig. 5). Two vertically stacked kneeling women, shown in the act of preparing some foodstuff, occupy the group centre. These two women are associated by proximity with small humans, likely representing three little girls and one boy. A crudely drawn warrior with a spear and two warriors brandishing a stick, facing each other, flank these central figures. A fourth warrior, advancing with a spear held horizontally, closes the composition to the upper left. By body proportions and stance, these warriors express a different style in respect of the previously mentioned male figures depicted on the panel. Very likely, they represent the last addition to the composition; perhaps attributable to the recent Camel Period since sticks or a kind of short assegai are the most commonly represented weapons in the paintings of the Ennedi late artistic tradition (Bailloud 1997).

At the shelter entrance, nearly in the open, enhanced images show the existence of much weathered human figures and cattle (Fig. 6). The partly retraced contour of the cow figure with forward-pointing horns shown

at the panel centre constitutes extraordinary evidence of the repainting practice among the Ennedi paintings of the pastoral era.

Overall, excluded the few horsemen and warriors with sticks belonging to the most recent painted layer, the Eli-2 shelter paintings appears as the collective portrait of a small community, celebrating its everyday life existence. They recall the variety of paintings derivative of the Tamada style attributes by Bailloud (1997) to the final Bovine Period under different style names, which could be more an expression of a regionalisation phenomenon as postulated by Lenssen-Erz (2012), rather than the result of a phased evolution of chronological value. The women with bell-shaped hairstyles distinguish a group of paintings not considered in the synthesis by Bailloud (1997) but well known outside his studied area centred on Fada (e.g., *Abri de la Danseuse* in Choppy et al. 1996).

Figure 5. Eli-2 shelter, upper edge of the main panel. At the centre, it is possible to recognise two kneeling women associated with small figures, likely representing three little girls and one boy. The two warriors brandishing sticks, facing each other, are probably a late addition, as well as the standing warrior and the warrior to the upper left, horizontally holding a long spear (upper panel: original picture – lower panel: DStretch enhanced version in CRGB colour space).

Figure 6. Faded human and cattle figures are present at the Eli-2 entrance, nearly in the open (upper panel: original picture – lower panel: DStretch enhanced version in LDS colour space). The IFRAO colour scale bar is 10 cm.

The Eli -3 shelter

Eli-3 corresponds to a small shallow shelter opening on the flank of a low sandstones knoll, west of the Amilianga pass. A multitude of simple crosses, the same motif documented in Eli-1, decorates the ceiling (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. The Eli-3 shelter is a small cavity, located on the camel trail to the west of the Amilianga pass. Painted crosses cover the ceiling (upper panel: original picture – lower panel: DStretch enhanced version in CRGB colour space).

Rock art sites in the Amilianga corridor

Within an embayment on the western mid-side of the Amilianga corridor, three small shelters open at a short distance one from each other, here named Amilianga 1, 2 and 3 (Fig. 1). Abandoned garbage indicates they have been in use in recent times as base camps by the local shepherds.

The Amilianga-1 shelter

The ceiling of Amilianga-1, the northernmost shelter (Fig. 8 and 9), although extensively sooted by fires, still preserves cattle figures (Fig. 10). The cattle painted on the eastern side bear traces of multiple percussions with a hard pointed tool, a not isolated iconoclastic act as the damaged cattle figures in Eli-1 prove (Menardi Noguera 2017, Fig. 4).

Figure 8. The Amilianga-1 shelter, still in use as a base camp by the local shepherds.

Figure 9. Campfires heavily damaged the Amilianga-1 shelter walls. However, the two sides of the triangularly shaped ceiling still preserve some painted cattle figures. The ones present on the eastern side bear evident traces of an iconoclastic act.

The Amilianga-2 shelter

The second shelter from the north, Amilianga-2, is a low tunnelling cavity (Fig. 10). Human figures painted in solid red decorate a protrusion jutting out of the ceiling at the southern entrance. Two rows of figures, hands in hands, wearing long gowns dotted in white, shown in frontal position with open legs, decorate the inner face of the protrusion (Fig. 11). Their hairstyles look like stylized caskets. The upper row is composed of ten individuals, being the one to the right reduced to tiny fragments. The lower row, partially destroyed by flaking and obliterated by mud wasp nests, counts seven figures. These two rows of figures likely represent

dancing women. Quite surprisingly, small holes, drilled in correspondence of the genitals of each figure, indicate the scene might have had an erotic connotation for someone.

Figure 10. The Amilinaga-2 shelter, a tunnelling cave, opens within a western embayment of the Amilianga corridor.

Figure 11. Amilianga-2 shelter; two rows of women wearing long gowns, dotted in white.

Two further rows of heavily damaged human figures decorate the outer face of the rock protrusion (Fig. 12). The upper row is composed of two standing warriors holding some undeterminable weapons. Double appendices topping their hairstyles, outlined in white and recumbent at the top end, likely represent feathers. Below these warriors, a row of seven almost destroyed figures is recognisable. The surviving fragments, reduced to the heads and upper arms, seem to reproduce the same motif of women hands in hands shown on the inner side of the shelter ceiling.

Figure 12. Amilianga-2 shelter; two standing warriors armed with undetermined weapons, shown above a row of fragmentary figures, likely representing women as indicates by the first figure to the left, wearing a gown.

In the open, on the eastern flank of the Amilianga-2 shelter, four engraved camels with humps stylized as triangles are present (Fig. 13). Although considered uninteresting by the French colonial soldiers who initiated rock art studies in the Ennedi (Choppy et al. 1996), this kind of engravings still demonstrate skill in producing neatly polished traits and also some dedication in carving and polishing the hump uniformly enough to reach an aesthetically pleasing effect. These camels look superior in quality of execution from the roughly pecked or scratched camels or the simple tribal marks that the present-day Ennedi guides sometimes indulge in producing when accompanying foreign visitors (Gauthier and Gauthier 2006; Lessen-Erz 2012).

Figure 13. Four engraved camel figures with the humped bodies stylized as triangles, carefully carved and polished, stand out near the eastern side of the Amilianga-2 shelter, in the open.

The Amilianga-3 shelter

The bottom wall of the Amilianga-3 shelter (Fig. 14) is decorated with few schematized cattle figures and one anthropomorphic figure, with an animal-shaped head and long hairs falling from the nape (Fig. 15 and 29). Feet finger, individually painted, give an apish appearance to this bizarre figure, which is holding with

the right hand a small, similarly drawn anthropomorphic figure. Being an isolated depiction, with no straightforward correspondence in the existing inventories of the Ennedi rock art, any interpretation is plausible. It could be the naïf depiction of a baboon with its offspring, a realistic theme since baboons still live in the Ennedi, or it could be even the depiction of a sorcerer or a supernatural being.

Figure 14. The Amilianga-3 shelter.

Figure 15. Two anthropomorphic figures and cattle figures on the eastern half of the ceiling of the Amilianga-3 shelter.

Figure 16. The impressive anthropomorphic with an animal-shaped head figure found on the ceiling of the Amilianga-3 (upper panel: original picture – lower panel: DStretch enhanced version in CRGB colour space).

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